

Relationship between Store Environment, Urge to Purchase and Impulsive Buying Behavior

Faisal Khan¹, Abdul Qayyum², Tehmeena Hanif³

Abstract

The store environment greatly influences impulsive buying behavior. Consumers mainly consider product attributes or functions when choosing a shopping destination, whereas, recently, the consumer has wanted to search for additional benefits. For consumers, the store's physical layout, lighting, music, and other sensory cues affect a customer's mood and influence their purchasing decisions. The current study aims to identify the relationship between the store environment with the urge to purchase and the urge to purchase with impulsive buying behaviour. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire from a sample of faculty members. Researchers have found that a pleasant store environment can increase customers' positive mood, leading to a greater urge to purchase and impulsive buying. Alternatively, an unpleasant store environment can negatively influence mood and reduce the likelihood of impulse purchases. The study findings revealed that the store environment positively correlates with the urge to purchase and the urge to purchase with impulsive buying behavior. Product placement, promotions, and pricing can influence the urge to purchase and impulsive buying behavior. Products placed strategically in high-traffic areas, on eye-level shelves, and at checkout, counters may increase impulse purchases. Limited-time offers and discounts, among others, can create an urgency that leads to impulse purchases. Therefore, retailers must understand the relationship between the store environment, the urge to purchase, and impulsive buying behavior to enhance their store design and marketing strategies. By creating a positive store environment and strategically placing products, retailers can increase the likelihood of impulse buying and ultimately improve their bottom line.

Keywords: Store Environment; Urge to Purchase; Impulsive Buying Behavior

1. Background of the study

Store environment, urge to purchase, and impulsive buying are essential concepts in consumer psychology and retail marketing. The relationship between these factors has been studied extensively in the literature, focusing on understanding the mechanisms that drive impulsive buying behavior in consumers (Akram, 2016). Researchers and marketers worldwide have acknowledged the relationship between store atmosphere and Impulse Buying Behavior (IBB). Creating a positive shopping experience for consumers depends heavily on the store environment. (Iyer, Blut, Xiao, & Grewal, 2020; Thompson & Prendergast, 2015). The impulse buying behavior (IBB) phenomenon is essential to retail businesses and marketers.

Moreover, impulse buying is characterized by hedonistic, unexpected, and compelling behavior (Park & Lennon, 2006; Zafar, Qiu, Li, Wang, & Shahzad, 2021). A wide range of product categories contributes to a substantial proportion of goods sold yearly (Hausman, 2000). Meanwhile, there has been growing research in the store environment, which studies how its various elements affect consumer behavior. Impulse buying and store atmosphere influence consumer behavior and buying patterns (Abrahams, 1997).

Impulse buying is defined as the act of buying something without a plan. The act of unplanned and unstructured purchase has traditionally been described as impulse buying (Rook & Fisher, 1995). A purchase is not based on a plan but on emotional triggers triggered by internal emotions. After the purchase has been made, a dynamic and cognitive reaction occurs (Parboteeah, 2005). Impulse buying is a significant aspect of consumer purchasing behavior. It is often associated with emotional factors such as excitement, pleasure, or anxiety. It occurs when a customer is shopping and experiences a strong urge to buy a product they see in the store, ultimately resulting in its purchase and acquisition (Akram, Hui, Khan, Hashim, & Rasheed, 2016). The importance of impulse buying for marketing managers has been well-known for some time. Research shows that most supermarket purchases are impulse purchases (Hashmi, Shu, & Haider, 2020; Parsad, Prashar, & Sahay, 2017).

It is estimated that impulse buying accounts for a significant portion of all goods sold worldwide yearly. In some types of products, this could be as high as 80%, according to several studies (Dumitrescu, 2016; Tran, 2021). Coca-Cola conducted research and found that 50% of consumers purchase groceries impulsively. Several factors influence impulsive buying behavior, such as culture, demographics, and the environment. Emotionally attached individuals are often most likely to approve of the product's effects immediately. Impulse shopping doesn't always result in satisfaction, causing shoppers to regret their quick decision (Zhou & Gu, 2015). Although consumers plan their shopping according to their characteristics, certain factors influence them to make unplanned purchases. POPAI reports that 76% of store shopping decisions are spontaneous (Fassnacht &

¹ Corresponding Author, Department of Management Sciences, University of Swabi, Pakistan, faisalkhanutm@yahoo.com

² Faculty of Management Sciences, Riphah International University, Islamabad, Pakistan

³ Lecturer, Department of Applied Psychology, National University fo Modern Languages, (NUML) Islamabad, Pakistan

Königsfeld, 2015; POPAI, 2012). Store displays and packaging designs capture customers in the retail sector. Additionally, the company uses state-of-art promotional strategies and store environments to boost sales. The phenomenon of impulse buying is universal, regardless of gender, age, or personality.

The urge to purchase is a psychological state characterized by a strong desire to buy something. It can be triggered by various factors such as product features, situational cues, and promotional offers. For example, seeing a limited-time deal or a discount on a product can create a sense of urgency and excitement, leading to an urge to purchase (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010). The study by Mohan, Sivakumaran, and Sharma (2013) showed that the store environment and the urge to buy positively correlate. In a pleasant environment, the urge to act is triggered when encountering an object. The act of catching the attention of an object in the environment without considering its consequences. Emotional purchases result in guilt and satisfaction because they cause emotional conflict. Perhaps this is why impulse purchases are not always made. Several studies have elaborated on the antecedents of impulse buying, including Bellini, Cardinali, and Grandi (2017) and Iyer, Blut, Xiao, and Grewal (2020), which emphasized individual characteristics, such as impulse buying tendency, situational factors, in-store advertisements, slack, signage display, and food consumption (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010; Pallikkara, Pinto, Hawaldar, & Pinto, 2021)(Khan., Sufyan, Hussain, & Gul, 2022).

According to Aghazadeh (2005), a store atmosphere is a complex combination of psychological factors and a store's physical and functional attributes. There is a strong correlation between the attributes of a store's atmosphere and the likelihood of shoppers remaining loyal to that store (Skandrani, Ben Dahmane Mouelhi, & Malek, 2011). The store environment influences customer buying behavior. The perception of a store as high on hedonic attributes made shoppers excited. In addition, it affects the customer's attitude towards service quality (Ashley, Ligas, & Chaudhuri, 2010). Customers need an efficient billing system, visual merchandising, informative signage, and friendly staff during their shopping experience. Aside from controlling the item purchased, it also controls time, store liking, money, seller quality, product evaluations, satisfaction, and store choice (Baker, Grewal, & Parasuraman, 1994; Roggeveen, Grewal, & Schweiger, 2020; Santos, Ramos, Sousa, Almeida, & Valeri, 2021). The store environment has received less attention as an antecedent to impulsive shopping. The study shows that crowding and other aspects of the store environment negatively affect purchase behavior (Mattila & Wirtz, 2008b). In the words of leading researchers Mattila and Wirtz (2008a), the importance of store atmosphere can be understood as follows: What you say, what you do, but how you make people feel will never be forgotten.

Many studies have investigated the association between store atmosphere and Impulsive buying behavior, but little has been done about the impact of demographic variables and the urge to purchase. However, developed countries such as Pakistan have notably neglected the influence of demographic variables in the context of store atmosphere, although demographic variables can play a vital role in consumers' behavior. This paper explores the relationship between store environment, urge to purchase and impulse buying behavior by incorporating the following research questions.

- To investigate the relationship between the store environment and the urge to purchase.
- To examine the relationship between the Urge to purchase and impulsive buying behavior.
- The researcher will identify the store environment based on music, display, friendly employees, and crowds in the current study.

2. Literature review

2.1. Impulsive Buying Behavior

The phenomenon of impulse purchases is not new; they have been observed to play an essential role in purchasing. The definition of an impulse purchase by Rook (1987) is when a consumer feels compelled to purchase something immediately following an intense urge to do so. Additionally, the study refers to it as a purchasing decision made impulsively without considering the product category or a specific goal. According to Beatty and Ferrel (1998), impulse buying is characterized by spontaneous and unplanned purchases. Previous studies from the 1950s show that it is associated with several product categories (Singh & Nayak, 2016). According to Lee and Kacen (2008), the desire to purchase something impulsively is irresistible, but the decision is less deliberate than planning to buy it.

Consumer behavior is relevant to both retail marketing and business. In retail stores, consumers with high Impulsive buying scores are likelier to buy impulsively (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998; Dawson & Kim, 2009). Luo (2005) stated that impulse buying behavior is more prevalent among singles, low socio-financial status individuals, materialistic individuals, and females. Cheng et al. (2009) argue that consumers with positive emotional reactions to the store atmosphere are likelier to make impulsive purchases. In addition, the importance of consumer impulse buying behavior in retail marketing and business cannot be overstated as Liao et al. (2009), low-cost vouchers, coupons, commercials and promotions, shop shows, staff behavior, and promoting value all play a significant role in impulsive buying. Various external factors influence a person's impulse buying behavior, including socioeconomic status, gender, lifestyle, and family background.

Store environments with high stimulation and pleasantness can increase impulse purchases (Youn & Faber, 2000). Customers were influenced by the product's appearance and background music when they made impulse purchases. Verplanken and Herabadi (2001), a pleasant environment triggers unplanned purchases and prepares consumers for spontaneous purchases. A pleasant store environment can encourage consumers to spend more time in the retail location, affiliate with service providers, and buy impulsively. The study found that store atmosphere and impulse buying are positively correlated. According to Bell et al. (2011), in-store advertising stimulates unplanned shopping. The above studies support the conclusion that the store atmosphere influences impulse buying.

2.2. Store environment

According to (1973), it is an environment designed to motivate buyers to buy while enhancing their likelihood of purchasing. Alternatively, it can be defined as a retail store's physical characteristics and surroundings that attract customers (Goldsmith & Goldsmith, 2002). There are several tangible aspects of a store atmosphere, according to (Youn & Faber, 2000), including equipment, cleanliness, theme colors, layout, product display, and eye-catching décor. Similarly, temperature, scent, music, and lighting are intangible factors. Shopping convenience is influenced by the store atmosphere, influencing the shopping experience (Brashear, Kashyap, Musante, & Donthu, 2009). The layout refers to the arrangement of store products, shopping carts, and aisles, their sizes and shapes, and their relationship. Retailers offer a wide variety of products as part of their product assortment. According to Mattila and Wirtz, 2001, various factors influence consumers' responses to a store, including the total configuration of cues (the Gestalt of consumers' perceptions of stores). The majority of previous studies have not operationalized store environment as a construct and have examined the influence of individual store elements, such as signage, product assortment, ambience, salesperson availability, and music, lighting, and scent, rather than the store environment as a whole (Beverland, Lim, Morrison, & Terziowski, 2006; Mattila & Wirtz, 2001). Despite Baker et al. (2002) taking into account multiple cues in one study (employee, design, and music perception), they were only interested in their individual effects, not the overall effect of the store environment.

Accordingly, this paper approaches the store environment as a combination of all the factors that affect it, including music, lighting, layout, and employees. It affects customers' perceptions and behavior in a broad sense.

2.3. Urge to Purchase

Another variable of the study is the urge to purchase. The urge to purchase is defined by Beatty and Ferrell (1998) as "a state of desire when confronted with an object in the environment" (p.172). Similarly, the author explained that all information comes from it and is how the selection is done. In addition to sudden and forced purchases, the author describes the pleasure of purchasing. To purchase the product or service, the shopper needs to view it first.

A desire to purchase is experienced while shopping in a pleasant environment. It is important to note that impulsive buying is one factor that influences the urge to buy impulsively (Mohan et al., 2013). It is not uncommon for consumers to feel sudden urges to purchase goods or services without knowing what they need. In 2014, KPMG found that personal factors influence 50% of people to explore, leading to impulse purchases. According to Lyer, Blut, Xiao and Grewal (2020), Beatty and Ferrell (1998) and Dholakia (2000), this happens suddenly and results in an actual desired outcome. The authors argue in previous research studies that a pleasant environment facilitates unplanned shopping by customers. The more time and thought customers spend in a friendly environment, the more likely they are to make impulse purchases. The environment in which consumers live can influence their urge to purchase or their internal states and characteristics. According to other studies, 50 percent of people want to urge to explore the product, which leads to impulsive buying.

2.4. Relationship between Store environment and Urge to Purchase

When a buyer is faced with an object in the shopping environment, such as a product, brand or model, the urge to buy impulsively is experienced (Dholakia, 2000). Beatty and Ferrell (1998) describe it as spontaneous, sudden, and preceding the impulse action. In a store, consumers experience more impulses and are more likely to make impulse purchases (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998). Generally, music enhances a store's atmosphere and can trigger an unplanned purchase (Turley & Milliman, 2000) or an impulse purchase. It is likely that some of these purchases are unplanned and may be impulse purchases due to listening to music for longer and spending more time and money than usual (Milliman, 1986). Eroglu and Machleit (2000), music and lighting stimulate impulse purchases. When the lighting in a store is appropriate, shoppers are more likely to explore the store and purchase items. It is possible to enhance the customer's perception of an interior by guiding them to critical sales points, cultivating an atmosphere of excitement, triggering positive emotions, or simply making key approach areas safe and visible through well-designed lighting systems. Sherman et al. (1997) found that ambient factors such as music and lighting can trigger impulsive purchases.

It facilitates access to information and aids the shopper in making decisions with an optimal layout. Aghazadeh (2005) found that peg boards and end caps induce an impulsive urge to purchase. A well-designed layout

influences even utilitarian shoppers by creating a sense of urgency. Salespeople can incite impulse purchases by guiding consumers through the store and the product range.

2.5. Relationship between Urge to Purchase and Impulsive Buying Behavior

When a consumer has a constant urge to buy, even if they try to control it to the greatest extent possible, he or they cannot resist the various purchasing encouragements offered during the shopping process (Baumeister, Twenge, & Nuss, 2002). As a result, consumers often struggle to resist impulse purchases despite their best efforts. Dholakia et al. (2000) and Mohan et al. (2013) define the urge to purchase as the impulse created when someone encounters an item, brand, or product in a store environment. In other words, an urge to buy or a desire to buy precedes impulsive consumption, so desire or a desire to buy should be positively related to impulse buying. Consumers experience an urge to buy when they encounter a product or item in a store. A person's likelihood of making an impulsive purchase increases when they experience a strong urge to buy (Mohan et al., 2013). Retail customers are primarily motivated by physical proximity to the object when they experience an impulse to purchase. Impulse purchases are most difficult to resist when consumers are confronted with attractive objects. Research conducted in the past has suggested that impulse buying is positively influenced by an urge to purchase (Foroughi, Buang, Senik, & Hajmisadeghi, 2013; Hanzaae & Taherikia, 2010).

H1: Store environment has a positive relationship with the urge to purchase.

H2: The store environment has a positive relationship with impulse buying behavior.

H3: The urge to purchase positively correlates with impulse buying behavior.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Data collection

Data were collected from males and females at three Swabi Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan district universities. A descriptive study was used to collect data on study variables to describe and explore how to store environments affect impulse and impulsive purchases. A simple random sampling method selected 260 samples from the target population following Krejcie, Morgan, and Ryan.

3.2. Measurement and data analysis

In this study, the Impulse buying behavior scale developed by Rook and Fisher [16] measures Impulse buying behavior. Based on a five-point Likert scale, it is composed of nine items ranging from 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree, where the sample item is “Whenever I go shopping, I end up buying things I hadn't planned on buying” Similarly, urge to purchase was measured by following Beatty and Ferrell, 1998 based on a five-point Likert scale. A sample item used is “Many unplanned purchases were made by me due to sudden urges”. Likewise, the store environment scale developed by [108] measures the store environment. Likert scale was used with the sample item “the store had appropriate display and setting”. The data was analyzed with the help of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

3.3. Instruments

The study questionnaire is composed of five sections. Section A consists of demographic variables. The first section relates to the store environment; the second discusses the urge to buy; the third is about personality traits; and the fourth is about impulsive buying behavior. Moreover, the researcher used the five-point Likert scale, primarily used in the social sciences, to collect the data. The store environment has been calculated using various subdimensions, including music, crowding, and a friendly environment. A total of 13 items were adapted from different studies. Three items have been adapted for calculating the urge to purchase. The reliability of the items reported in the study was 0.85 and 0.80, respectively. Seven items were adapted from Badgaiyan and Verma for calculating Impulsive buying behavior.

4. Data analysis and Findings

A statistical test of the preliminary analysis was conducted before proceeding to the final data analysis. Moreover, a different multivariate test was calculated to ensure that the following assumptions of multivariate analysis were not violated in determining the basic social science standard. These tests include normality and outlining.

In the study, the first test was the normality of the data. According to Hair and Anderson (2010), normality is calculated by comparing the histogram residual and standard distribution curve (Hair & Anderson, 2010; Murtagh & Heck, 2012). Furthermore, the study explained that the bell-shaped symmetrical curve in the histogram has a higher frequency in the middle and a lower frequency at the edges (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2006; Rocha, 2008). In the graphical presentation, the bell shape shows that the data is normally distributed. In the current study, the normality of the data was confirmed on the value of skewness and kurtosis. According to Byrne (2013), skewness values are acceptable within the range of ± 2 and kurtosis's acceptable range is ± 7 . Therefore, the test in Table 1 shows that the data is normal and ready for final analysis.

On the other hand, an outlier refers to values that are lower or higher than the other values in the data set. The result clearly shows that most data are similar and confirms the outlier assumption. Figures 1 and 2 show no outlier and the values are within the range and have no outliers.

Table 1: Normality Test

Variables	N	Skewness		Kurtosis	
		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Store environment	240	-.011	.157	-1.042	.313
Urge to Purchase	240	.386	.157	-.149	.313
Impulsive Buying Behavior	240	-.013	.157	.183	.313

Figure 1 Scatter Plot of SE and UTP

Figure 2 Scatter Plot of UTP and IBB

4.1. Descriptive Statistics and Reliability

Descriptive statistics calculate the mean, minimum, maximum and standard deviation data. It organizes and explains the data (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016; Sekaran., 2005). Moreover, statistics provide a brief overview of a data set representing a whole or sample population. The primary purpose of descriptive statistics is to review a given set of data using descriptive coefficients that represent the population as a whole or a sample. Furthermore, ANOVA, t-independence tests, and average descriptive statistics have been used to investigate variations in occurrences between respondents according to their differences. The descriptive statistics find the mean and standard deviation in the current study. Table 3 shows the values of each variable. Based on research, self-administration is reliable because consistency is possessed.

Furthermore, Polit and Beck (2004) define reliability that “a quantitative instrument is a major criterion for assessing its quality and adequacy” (p.416). In the current study, the researcher calculated the reliability based on Cronbach’s alpha value. Table 3 shows the reliability values for each variable within the acceptable range. Furthermore, an expert in the relevant field validated the scale’s validity.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics and Reliability

Vatable	N	Cronbach’s Alpha	Mean	Standard Deviation
Store environment	240	0.86	2.626	0.627
Urge to purchase	240	0.78	2.535	0.829
Impulsive Buying Behavior	240	0.83	2.686	0.697

As discussed in chapter 3, the data has been collected from three Higher Education Institutions in the district of Swabi. In addition, self-administrated questionnaires were distributed during visits and through Google Forms researchers; the sample comprised 260 employees of 798 HEIs; 330 questionnaires were distributed to respondents. After personal requests, the response rate was 72%.

4.2. Demographic Characteristics

Demographic characteristics significantly influence overall results because of their distinctive importance. Table 4 shows a detailed description of the respondents. A detailed description of the respondents is presented in this section, where 240 faculty members work at HEIs in district Swabi. Moreover, most of the members were

females, female (60 percent) and Assistant professors (55.8 percent) and the income level of the respondents was 22.5 percent in 50001 to 100000 and 55 percent were in the range of 100001 to 150000.

4.3. Relationship between store environment, Urge to purchase and Impulsive Buying behavior

The proposed model consists of direct relationships and indirect effects. A direct relationship between the store environment, the urge to purchase and impulsive buying behavior. Therefore, correlation analysis has been adopted to analyze the relationship among the variables. The study's first hypothesis was a positive relationship between the store environment and the urge to purchase. Table 4 shows the result of the correlational analysis that the store environment positively correlates with the urge to purchase among the faculty members of universities in district Swabi KP, Pakistan. In addition, Table 5 shows a positive relationship between the Urge to purchase and impulsive buying behavior among the faculty members.

Table 3: Demographic Characteristics

Demographics		Frequency	% Total
Gender	Male	96	40
	Female	144	60
Designation	Lecturer	85	35.4
	Assistant Professor	134	55.8
	Associate Professor	15	6.3
	Professor	6	2.5
Income	Less Than 50000	9	3.8
	51001 to 100000	54	22.5
	100001 to 150000	132	55
	150001 to 200000	24	10.7
	Above 200001	21	8.75

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

	Store environment	Urge to purchase	Impulsive Buying Behavior
Store environment	1		
Urge to purchase	.887**	1	
Impulsive Buying Behavior	.830**	.871**	1

**Significant at 0.01

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Before starting the discussion on the objectives, a brief introduction regarding objectives, the study discusses the store environment is more significant for customers and consumers in buying the product where they buy the unplanned product. In addition, this unplanned shopping was due to an environment that reflects the customers' minds. Furthermore, the study investigates the urge to purchase with impulsive buying behavior. They shop for the product without consultation with their drawbacks or previous experience.

The study investigated the relationship between the store environment and the urge to purchase among district Swabi Higher Education Institutions faculty members. Based on the data, correlation analysis shows a very high relationship between the store environment and the urge to purchase. The study reveals a positive relationship between the store environment and the urge to purchase. It means that store environments like music, display of products and layout, have an essential role in the customer's urge to purchase the products, which was also recommended in the study (Husnain, Rehman, Syed, & Akhtar, 2019). It further explained that retailers try to make a pleasant environment for their customers or consumers and intend for them to purchase the product. In addition, the retailer is trying to be more equipped to make the customers or consumers fresh and relaxed for more urge to purchase. The results align with previous studies (Atulkar & Kesari, 2018; Mohan et al., 2013). Moreover, it clarifies that most customers or consumers decide on the spot. The study mentioned that company management should focus on the dynamic environment (Awan & Abbas, 2015). Another reason to buy a product is the longer you stay in the store, the more you'll buy compared to buying quickly (Foroughi, Buang, & Sadeghi, 2012).

The second objective was determining the relationship between the urge to purchase and impulsive buying behavior. Based on the study analysis, the correlation results strongly correlate with impulsive buying behavior,

which is 0.87. it means that the urge to purchase has an essential role in the decision of the consumer impulsively. The customers or consumers have no plans for shopping, but still, they do unplanned shopping. Aside from that, the customer did not focus on the post-experience of the product. This study supported the results of Beatty & Ferrell, 1998; Mohan et al., 2013, indicating that market managers acknowledged the role of impulsive buying ((Beatty & Ferrell, 1998; Mohan et al., 2013). In addition, they also admitted and reported that 50 to 70 percent of consumers are involved in impulsive buying during shopping in supermarkets. A highly competitive marketplace has made it more difficult for marketers to differentiate their stores solely based on their consumers' characteristics, prices, advertisements, promotions and locations. Therefore, the company applies additional upcoming and cross-selling strategies. The firm focuses on the existing customers that can be cultivated and extended, which is essential for customer relationship management (Berman, Evans, & Chatterjee, 2018).

5.1. Implications of the study

This section indicates the implications regarding store environment, urge to purchase and impulsive buying behavior for customers or consumers. It improves the body of knowledge and Stimuli Organism Response (S-O-R) underpinning theory. The study showed that the store environment is an essential factor influencing consumer intentions toward unplanned shopping. The study concluded that there is a positive relationship between the variables. From the data, it has been revealed that most of the respondents were females who are motivated by a more pleasant environment.

Moreover, the current study findings were significant in both cases of retailers, regardless of whether they intend to start a business. They may set up or update a new setup (Awan & Abbas, 2015). The study confirmed the involvement of the urge to purchase in the framework, as suggested in previous studies (Badgaiyan & Verma, 2015). The urge to purchase depends on the store environment, further influencing the consumer to further shopping, which is unplanned and increases the impulsiveness of the consumer.

This study provides valuable perceptions on the impact of store environment and impulsive buying behavior in district Swabi among the faculty member of higher education intuitions. By studying variable knowledge, retailers can arrange all the promises to their customers or consumers by formulating new strategies to organize their dynamic and pleasant store environment. The retailer can generate their strategies of promotions, layout, lighting, avoiding crowds and design to increase sales. This study's result recommended that the retailer manager manage their store environment for highly involved consumers. The manager should try to attract a more efficient and effective impulsive buyer.

Moreover, this study helps the retailer focus on customer-related variables' needs. This study helps managers with the behavior of the customers or consumers. Thus, this study contributes to the marketing area and gains a competitive advantage. Moreover, the findings also suggested that policymakers need consumer feedback to increase the company's profit. In addition, policymakers need to improve the role and importance of the consumer. To increase the impulsiveness of consumers, the marketer can identify the triggers of impulsive buying behavior.

5.2. Limitations and Recommendations of the study

The current research has strengths and benefits but has some deficiencies that affect its findings. The study aims to understand the role of the store environment on impulsive buying behavior in the market among faculty members in the district of Swabi KP, Pakistan. Moreover, several decisions were made during the current study based on the situation and needs, which affected the study's methodology, data collection, analysis, and results. Several restrictions were also placed on the study to meet the research objectives and answer the research questions. The current study adopted a quantitative approach; combining quantitative and qualitative approaches may produce different results.

In addition, the study uses a cross-sectional method due to the shortage of time to complete the degree on time and financial constraints; Data might be more in-depth and informative if the longitudinal design is applied and reveals variation. Furthermore, a sample of the current study might be a potential limitation because the data was collected from the district Swabi Higher Education Institutions. As a result, this study does not represent the opinions of all districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and all Pakistani provinces. Future studies should include more provinces, both public and private Higher Education Institutions, for better results.

Currently, researchers are studying the effects of the store environment and the urge to purchase on the impulsive buying behavior of customers. In the future, the researchers may decide to incorporate some other moderators between the studies, such as self-concept, dimensions of the store environment, advertisements, consumer involvement, etc., to measure the impact of their relationship. Moreover, to check the impulsive buying behavior among the faculty members of the Swabi district in particular and other areas of Pakistan in general, the researcher needs to study the effect of demographic factors on impulsive buying behavior.

References

Abrahams, B. (1997). It's all in the mind. *Marketing*, 27(1), 31-33.

- Aghazadeh, S. M. (2005). Layout strategies for retail operations: A case study. *Management Research News*, 28(10), 31-46.
- Akram, U., Hui, P., Khan, M. K., Hashim, M., & Rasheed, S. (2016). Impact of store atmosphere on impulse buying behaviour: Moderating effect of demographic variables. *International Journal of u-and e-Service, Science and Technology*, 9(7), 43-60.
- Ashley, C., Ligas, M., & Chaudhuri, A. (2010). Can hedonic store environments help retailers overcome low store accessibility? *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 18(3), 249-262.
- Atulkar, S., & Kesari, B. (2018). Role of consumer traits and situational factors on impulse buying: does gender matter? *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 46(4), 386-405.
- Awan, A. G., & Abbas, N. (2015). Impact of demographic factors on impulse buying behavior of consumers in Multan-Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(22), 96-105.
- Babin, B., & Darden, W. Griffin. 2004. Impulsive Buying Varies by Product. *Journal of advertising research*, 18, 15-18.
- Badgaiyan, A. J., & Verma, A. (2015). Does urge to buy impulsively differ from impulsive buying behaviour? Assessing the impact of situational factors. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 22, 145-157.
- Baker, J., Grewal, D., & Parasuraman, A. (1994). The influence of store environment on quality inferences and store image. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 22(4), 328-339.
- Baker, J., Parasuraman, A., Grewal, D., & Voss, G. B. (2002). The influence of multiple store environment cues on perceived merchandise value and patronage intentions. *Journal of Marketing*, 66(2), 120-141.
- Baumeister, R. F., Twenge, J. M., & Nuss, C. K. (2002). Effects of social exclusion on cognitive processes: anticipated aloneness reduces intelligent thought. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 83(4), 817.
- Beatty, S. E., & Ferrell, M. E. (1998). Impulse buying: Modeling its precursors. *Journal of Retailing*, 74(2), 169-191.
- Bell, J., Huber, J., & Viscusi, W. K. (2011). Survey mode effects on valuation of environmental goods. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 8(4), 1222-1243.
- Bellini, S., Cardinali, M. G., & Grandi, B. (2017). A structural equation model of impulse buying behaviour in grocery retailing. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 36, 164-171.
- Berman, B., Evans, J. R., & Chatterjee, P. (2018). *Retail management: A strategic approach*: Pearson Education Limited.
- Beverland, M., Lim, E. A. C., Morrison, M., & Terziovski, M. (2006). In-store music and consumer-brand relationships: Relational transformation following experiences of (mis) fit. *Journal of Business Research*, 59(9), 982-989.
- Brashear, T. G., Kashyap, V., Musante, M. D., & Donthu, N. (2009). A profile of the internet shopper: evidence from six countries. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 17(3), 267-282.
- Byrne, B. M. (2013). *Structural equation modeling with AMOS: Basic concepts, applications, and programming*: Routledge.
- Cheng, F.-F., Wu, C.-S., & Yen, D. C. (2009). The effect of online store atmosphere on consumer's emotional responses—an experimental study of music and colour. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 28(4), 323-334.
- Dawson, S., & Kim, M. (2009). External and internal trigger cues of impulse buying online. *Direct Marketing: An International Journal*.
- Dholakia, U. M. (2000). Temptation and resistance: An integrated model of consumption impulse formation and enactment. *Psychology & Marketing*, 17(11), 955-982.
- Dumitrescu, F. M. (2016). The dimension of the socio-cultural brand of Coca-Cola. *Social Sciences and Education Research Review*, 3(2), 48-54.
- Fassnacht, M., & Königsfeld, J. A. (2015). Sales promotion management in retailing: Tasks, benchmarks, and future trends. *Marketing Review St. Gallen*, 32(3), 67-77.
- Foroughi, A., Buang, N. A., & Sadeghi, R. H. M. (2012). Exploring the influence of situational factors (money & time available) on impulse buying behaviour among different ethics. *International Journal of Fundamental Psychology & Social Sciences (IJFPSS)*, 2(2), 41-44.
- Foroughi, A., Buang, N. A., Senik, Z. C., & Hajmiasadeghi, R. S. (2013). Impulse buying behavior and moderating role of gender among Iranian shoppers. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 3(4), 760-769.
- Ghosh, P., Tripathi, V., & Kumar, A. (2010). Customer expectations of store attributes: A study of organized retail outlets in India. *Journal of Retail & Leisure Property*, 9, 75-87.
- Goldsmith, R. E., & Goldsmith, E. B. (2002). Buying apparel over the Internet. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*.

- Gravetter, F., & Wallnau, L. (2006). *Statistics for the behavioral sciences*: Cengage Learning.
- Hair, J. F., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis* (7th ed.): Prentice Hall Higher Education.
- Hanzaee, K. H., & Taherikia, F. (2010). Impulse buying: an Iranian model. *China-USA Business Review*, 9(12), 31.
- Hashmi, H. B. A., Shu, C., & Haider, S. W. (2020). Moderating effect of hedonism on store environment-impulse buying nexus. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 48(5), 465-483.
- Hausman, A. (2000). A multi-method investigation of consumer motivations in impulse buying behavior. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 17(5), 403-426.
- Husnain, M., Rehman, B., Syed, F., & Akhtar, M. W. (2019). Personal and in-store factors influencing impulse buying behavior among generation Y consumers of small cities. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 7(1), 92-107.
- Iyer, G. R., Blut, M., Xiao, S. H., & Grewal, D. (2020). Impulse buying: a meta-analytic review. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 48(3), 384-404.
- Khan., F., Sufyan, M., Hussain, A., & Gul, A. (2022). Moderating Role Of Transformational Leadership On Servant Leadership With Emotional Exhaustion Among Health Care Employees. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(8), 10697-10713.
- Kotler, P. (1973). Atmospheric as a marketing tool. *Journal of Retailing*, 49(4), 48-64.
- Lee, J. A., & Kacen, J. J. (2008). Cultural influences on consumer satisfaction with impulse and planned purchase decisions. *Journal of Business Research*, 61(3), 265-272.
- Liao, S. L., Shen, Y. C., & Chu, C. H. (2009). The effects of sales promotion strategy, product appeal and consumer traits on reminder impulse buying behaviour. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 33(3), 274-284.
- Luo, X. (2005). How does shopping with others influence impulsive purchasing? *Journal of consumer psychology*, 15(4), 288-294.
- Machleit, K. A., & Eroglu, S. A. (2000). Describing and measuring emotional response to shopping experience. *Journal of Business Research*, 49(2), 101-111.
- Mattila, A. S., & Wirtz, J. (2001). Congruency of scent and music as a driver of in-store evaluations and behavior. *Journal of Retailing*, 77(2), 273-289.
- Mattila, A. S., & Wirtz, J. (2008a). The role of store environmental stimulation and social factors on impulse purchasing. *Journal of services marketing*.
- Mattila, A. S., & Wirtz, J. (2008b). The role of store environmental stimulation and social factors on impulse purchasing. *Journal of Services marketing*, 22(7), 562-567.
- Milliman, R. E. (1986). The influence of background music on the behavior of restaurant patrons. *Journal of Consumer research*, 13(2), 286-289.
- Mohan, G., Sivakumaran, B., & Sharma, P. (2013). Impact of store environment on impulse buying behavior. *European journal of marketing*.
- Murtagh, F., & Heck, A. (2012). *Multivariate data analysis* (Vol. 131): Springer Science & Business Media.
- Parboteeah, D. V. (2005). A model of online impulse buying: An empirical study.
- Park, & Lennon, S. J. (2006). Psychological and environmental antecedents of impulse buying tendency in the multichannel shopping context. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 23(2), 56-66.
- Parsad, C., Prashar, S., & Sahay, V. (2017). Impact of Impulsive Personality Traits and Store Environment on Impulse Buying Behavior. *Journal of Business & Management*, 23(1), 1-24.
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2004). *Nursing research: Principles and methods*: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- POPAI, T. (2012). Shoppers Are Making More Purchasing Decisions In-Store Than Ever Before. *Press Release*.
- Rocha, D. J. (2008). Strengthening the validity of software process improvement measurements through statistical analysis: A case study at Ericsson AB. *rapport nr.: report/IT University of Göteborg 2008: 082*.
- Roggeveen, A. L., Grewal, D., & Schweiger, E. B. (2020). The DAST framework for retail atmospherics: The impact of in-and out-of-store retail journey touchpoints on the customer experience. *Journal of Retailing*, 96(1), 128-137.
- Rook, D. W. (1987). The buying impulse. *Journal of Consumer research*, 14(2), 189-199.
- Rook, D. W., & Fisher, R. J. (1995). Normative influences on impulsive buying behavior. *Journal of Consumer research*, 22(3), 305-313.
- Santos, V., Ramos, P., Sousa, B., Almeida, N., & Valeri, M. (2021). Factors influencing touristic consumer behaviour. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 35(3), 409-429.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*: John Wiley & Sons.

- Sekaran., U. (2005). *Research Methods For Business: A Skill-Building Approach*: John Wiley & Sons Australia, Limited.
- Singh, R., & Nayak, J. K. (2016). Effect of family environment on adolescent compulsive buying: mediating role of self-esteem. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 28(3), 396-419.
- Skandrani, H., Ben Dahmane Mouelhi, N., & Malek, F. (2011). Effect of store atmospherics on employees' reactions. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 39(1), 51-67.
- Thompson, E. R., & Prendergast, G. P. (2015). The influence of trait affect and the five-factor personality model on impulse buying. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 76, 216-221.
- Tran, V. T. (2021). Exhibiting Coca-Cola at universal exhibitions. *Food, Culture & Society*, 24(2), 269-290.
- Turley, L. W., & Milliman, R. E. (2000). Atmospheric effects on shopping behavior: a review of the experimental evidence. *Journal of Business Research*, 49(2), 193-211.
- Verplanken, B., & Herabadi, A. (2001). Individual differences in impulse buying tendency: Feeling and no thinking. *European Journal of personality*, 15(1_suppl), S71-S83.
- Youn, S., & Faber, R. J. (2000). Impulse buying: its relation to personality traits and cues. *ACR North American Advances*.
- Zafar, A. U., Qiu, J., Li, Y., Wang, J., & Shahzad, M. (2021). The impact of social media celebrities' posts and contextual interactions on impulse buying in social commerce. *Computers in human behavior*, 115, 106178.
- Zhou, H., & Gu, Z. (2015). The effect of different price presentations on consumer impulse buying behavior: The role of anticipated regret. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 5(01), 27-36.